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USE OF INTERACTIVE FORMS AND METHODS OF LEARNING TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF LEARNING STUDENTS IN THE LESSON

Resume: The article discusses the ways of maintenance and gives theoretical materials on the preparation of students of secondary educational schools in the classroom of fine art. Theoretical materials have been developed on various topics that develop students' images that serve to shape the skills of their use of modern computer technologies.

Key words: Picture, technology, color, creativity, memory, attention, teaches, think, analyze, compare, compose, imagine, fine art, reproduction, painting, artist.

The value of interactive forms and teaching methods. An interactive mode of work implies the interaction of a teacher and a student, in which the teacher receives an adequate response from the students for each of his actions.

The main significance of interactive forms and teaching methods is to ensure the achievement of a number of important educational goals:

- Stimulation of motivation and interest in the field of the studied subjects.
- Increasing the level of activity and independence of students.
- Development of skills to analyze the criticality of thinking, interaction, communication.
- Self-development and development, thanks to the activation of mental activity and interaction with the teacher and other participants in the educational process.

Modern classifications of didactic methods.

Teaching method is a way of interrelated activities of teachers and students, aimed at solving complex problems of the educational process.

There are several classifications of teaching methods. Among teachers, the traditional classification is widespread, reflected in all textbooks of didactics: verbal, visual, practical methods. This classification is based on the method of presenting information to students. If the classification is based on the degree of independence of the student in acquiring knowledge, we get a different set: reproductive, partially exploratory, exploratory, research. There is also a classification: explanatory-illustrative, programmed, problematic, model. Such methods are called interactive today.

To apply interactive methods, the teacher must learn to work in a mode of creative developmental learning. The development of problem-search methods is the basis for the organization of creative research activities of students, and, consequently, the basis of

interactive learning. With interactive learning, it is important to teach the student to work in the entire cycle:

- search and isolation of leading problems
- Ranking problems in order of importance
- problem analysis,
- determination of goals, objectives of activities,
- development of possible solutions,
- selection of the best solutions,
- determination of a mechanism for solving problems,
- drawing up a program and work plan.

The teacher should strive to build the whole range of ideas and actions that need to be incorporated into the process of interactive learning.

"There are only as many good methods as there are good teachers."

What are the methods of activating the cognitive activity of students.

1. The use of non-traditional forms of the lesson.

There are several dozen types of non-standard lessons, their names give some idea of the goals, objectives, methods of their implementation. The most common: immersion lessons, competition lessons, theatrical lessons, peer learning lessons, truth-seeking lessons, etc. All teachers should practice such lessons, but it is not advisable to turn non-standard lessons into the main form of work, to lead them into a system due to the lack of serious cognitive work.

2. Use of non-traditional forms of training sessions

- Integrated, united by a single theme or problem.
- Combined, contributing to long-term concentration of attention and systemic perception of educational material.
- Project classes aimed at fostering a culture of cooperation and a culture of mental and creative work.

3. Application of game forms, teaching methods and techniques.

Game forms:

- Role playing
- Didactic
- Imitation
- Organizational and activity

4. Wide application of the problem-task approach (a system of cognitive and practical tasks, problematic issues, situations).

Types of situations:

- Situation of choice, when you need to choose the right one from the already available solutions.
- Situation-uncertainty, when there are ambiguous decisions due to lack of data.
- Situation-conflict which contains in its basis struggle and unity of opposites.
- An unexpected situation that surprises the trainees with its unusualness.

- Situation-suggestion, when the teacher involves students in an active search for new patterns.

- Situation-refutation, if it is necessary to prove the inconsistency of any decision.

5. The use of all forms of student work.

Forms of study work:

- Collective
- Group
- Individual
- Frontal
- Brigadier
- Paired

6. Increasing the proportion of interactive teaching methods.

What methods are interactive? Interactive methods are based on the degree of independence of students in acquiring knowledge and the level of research activity of students, they are directly interconnected and help to assess the degree of student activity.

7. Use of all methods of motivation and stimulation of students.

Motivation is understood as a set of driving forces that induce a person to activity and give this activity a certain meaning. Students can and should be formed sustainable motivation in self-development, acquisition of new knowledge and skills. The motivation for self-development is due to the desire to become more successful. There are 4 groups of motivation methods:

Emotional: encouragement, creating situations of success, stimulating assessment, free choice of tasks, satisfaction of the desire to be a significant person.

Cognitive: reliance on life experience, taking into account cognitive interests, creating problem situations, stimulating the search for alternative solutions, performing creative tasks. **Volitional:** informing about the required results, the formation of a responsible attitude, the identification of cognitive difficulties, self-assessment and correction of one's activities, the formation of the ability to exercise reflection, forecasting future activities.

Social: the development of the desire to be useful, the creation of a situation of mutual assistance, empathy, the search for contacts and cooperation, interest in the results of collective work, the organization of self- and mutual verification.

Thus, motivation is the main condition for interactive learning, therefore, it is important for any teacher to identify the presence and content of students' educational needs, and systematically use optimal methods of motivation in each lesson in order to implement a student-centered developmental approach.

There is a lot of talk about the informatization of education. This is understood as the optimal use of modern information and communication technologies to solve the pedagogical and psychological goals of education.

Since learning is primarily an information process, the use of computer information technology is especially important.

Information technologies in education are often identified with technologies for the study and application of computer technology in solving educational problems.

There are three areas of informatization of education:

1. As an object of learning
2. As a means of organizing the educational process
3. As a learning tool.

Solving the problems of the first direction is the subject of the course "Informatics, information and communication technologies"

The process of processing documentation on the educational process is associated with the second direction: processing information about students, teachers, and the results of the educational process.

The third direction is related to the ability of the computer to act as an effective means of increasing the effectiveness of learning, if used as a new learning tool. ICT can be used as an information system, as a source of information to perform creative tasks, to significantly expand the visibility of learning, as well as to quickly control the assimilation of knowledge and skills by students. The use of ICT as a learning tool increases the motivation of learning due to the interest of students in computer-related activities.

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